

Net Profit Margin (NPM) Ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the research mapping regarding the Net Profit Margin (NPM) ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking using a mix-method approach, namely the VOSviewer bibliometric study and Library Research. Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications around the NPM ratio; (2) mapping the results of the VOSviewer bibliometric visualization around the NPM ratio based on the number of clusters and their items; and (3) mapping research topics around the NPM ratio using a Library Research study. The results showed that: (1) based on the distribution of journal publications, there were 885 journal publications regarding the NPM ratio; (2) based on the mapping of the VOSviewer bibliometric study, the network visualization results around the NPM ratio are divided into 4 clusters and 175 topic items; (3) based on the mapping of Library Research studies, there are 49 topics around the influence of the NPM ratio and 41 topics about the determinants of the NPM ratio. The implications and contributions of this research are to map research topics around NPM ratios in Islamic and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers so that they can be a reference for subsequent researchers.

Keywords: Net Profit Margin (NPM), Bibliometrics, VOSviewer, Library Research, Islamic and Conventional Banking

Introduction

the Net Profit Margin (NPM) ratio in banking has been going on for quite a long time and is still relevant today. This ratio is often used by financial analysts, investors and regulators to evaluate a bank's financial performance and the bank's ability to generate net profits. In general, the higher the NPM ratio, the better the bank's financial performance. However, in some cases, a high NPM ratio can also indicate unethical business practices, such as reducing service quality or charging high fees to customers (Mahdatika, 2021). The development of the use of the NPM ratio in banking cannot be separated from changes in economic conditions and the development of the banking industry itself. Along with these changes, the use of the NPM ratio in measuring bank financial performance has also experienced developments.

Currently, the NPM ratio is not only used as a benchmark for bank financial performance in general, but is also used to compare financial performance between similar banks, monitor bank profit growth over time, and assess bank financial risk and stability. This ratio is also often used as an indicator in measuring a bank's financial health. However, it should be noted that NPM is not the only indicator used to evaluate a bank's financial performance. There are also several other financial ratios used, such as Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE). The use of financial ratios in the banking industry also continues to grow along with technological developments and changes in increasingly complex economic conditions. Therefore, it is important for decision makers in banking to continuously update their knowledge and pay attention to the latest trends in the use of ratios finance,

including NPM, to ensure the bank's financial performance remains healthy and sustainable (Kesuma, 2022).

Several studies on NPM in banking try to study the influence of certain factors on bank financial performance as measured by NPM. First, research that discusses the influence of bank size, leverage, credit risk, liquidity and macroeconomic factors on NPM. The results of these studies show that there is a relationship between these factors and bank financial performance as measured by NPM (Rahmani, 2019). Second, research that compares the financial performance of banks in various countries using the NPM ratio as one of the indicators. This research tries to identify differences in the factors that influence NPM in different countries and how these factors influence bank financial performance (Fauziah, 2020). Third, other research related to NPM in banking is the use of the NPM ratio as an indicator in measuring bank financial risk. Several studies have tried to evaluate bank financial risk using NPM as the main indicator, and the results show that the NPM ratio can indeed be used as an indicator of bank financial risk (Kholis, 2021). Fourth, the research also examines the influence of monetary and fiscal policy on NPM and bank financial performance. Several studies try to evaluate the impact of interest rates, inflation, and fiscal policy on NPM and bank financial performance, as well as how banks can manage these risks to maintain good financial performance. In the context of an increasingly complex banking industry, research on NPM and the factors that influence bank financial performance will continue to develop. This is important to help decision makers in banking manage risk and improve bank financial performance in a sustainable manner (Sucipto, 2022).

The aim of this research is to map research topics around NPM in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions using: (1) the VOSviewer bibliometric method to analyze and study maps of literature development in publications in a scientific field by creating a metadata network map; and (2) Library Research studies to analyze, identify and review articles from the accredited national journal Sinta. Differences in this research with previous research, this research explains all research topics surrounding NPM. This can be a reference for other researchers who wish to research NPM. The implication and contribution of this research is to map topics that are often researched by researchers, so that they can identify research gaps, and can become a reference for subsequent researchers.

Literature Review

Net Profit Margin (NPM) in banking is one of the financial ratios used to measure the profitability of a bank. NPM calculates what percentage of net profit is generated by the bank from the income earned. NPM is calculated by dividing the net profit (net profit) obtained by the bank during a period by the income (net revenue) generated by the bank in the same period. In this case, net revenue is total income minus operating expenses. In general, the higher the NPM, the better the financial performance of a bank. However, it should be noted that NPM can be influenced by various factors such as operational costs, interest rates and credit risk. Therefore, it is necessary to carry out a more in-depth analysis to assess a bank's financial performance holistically (Mahdatika, 2021).

Bibliometric studies are analytical methods used to measure and analyze literature or scientific publications in a particular field. This method

uses bibliographic and statistical data to evaluate the number of publications, authors, subjects, and citations of a particular field of study or topic. Bibliometric studies can provide a better understanding of the influence of a study or topic within the academic community, as well as measuring the quantity and quality of scientific work. This method can also help in forecasting research trends, determining the importance of certain topics, and identifying research collaborations. Data used in bibliometric studies can come from various sources such as bibliographic databases, scientific journals, or websites. The analysis carried out can include statistical calculations such as the number of publications, authors, subjects and citations, as well as network analysis and visual diagrams to show the relationship between scientific works produced in a particular field (Dubyna et al., 2022).

VOSviewer is free software used to perform bibliometric analysis and network visualization. This software was developed by Eindhoven University of Technology and can be used to analyze and visualize bibliometric data such as scientific publications, citations and research collaborations. VOSviewer allows users to import bibliometric data from various sources such as Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar, and process and analyze that data in various forms. Once the data has been processed, this software can produce network visualizations, including cluster mapping diagrams, bibliographic network diagrams, and co-citation diagrams. In addition, VOSviewer is also equipped with features such as co-occurrence analysis and bibliographic analysis, which can help users to better understand research patterns, the relationship between research topics, as well as the influence and popularity of scientific publications. VOSviewer is one of the most popular bibliometric software, especially among academics and researchers. This software can help users to gain better insight into scientific publications in a particular field and makes it possible to visualize data in an effective and interesting manner (van Eck NJ, 2022).

Library Research study is a research method carried out by systematically analyzing literature sources or scientific publications that are relevant to a particular research topic. This method allows researchers to understand current issues, trends and recent developments in a particular field, as well as identify knowledge gaps or problems that remain unsolved. Library Research studies are generally carried out by searching for and evaluating articles, books, theses, dissertations and other scientific publications related to the research topic. In addition, this method also involves critical analysis of these sources, with the aim of identifying similarities and differences between the views and opinions of different authors. The results of the Library Research study can be used as a basis for designing further research, develop new theories, or assess the progress of research that has been carried out in a particular field. This method can also help to identify knowledge gaps in a particular field, as well as provide a basis for determining research priorities and developing action plans to solve problems that remain unsolved. In general, Library Research studies are very important in the research process because they can help researchers understand the literature relevant to the research topic, identify knowledge gaps in a particular field, and design effective research (El-Halaby et al., 2021).

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in Library Research studies. The research object is Net Profit Margin (NPM).

Type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles on NPM in Islamic and Conventional Banking.

The source of data collection came from searching the accredited national journal Sinta via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) and the Perish/Harzing software. Tool Data analysis using Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer software. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category with the key words " Net Profit Margin " and "NPM" over the entire year period; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding NPM using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop based on publication year; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and journal publication trends around NPM using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping topics research around NPM uses Library Research studies (Budianto, 2023) (Gozali et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Rofika et al., 2023) (Budianto, Dewi, et al., 2023) (Budianto, Saputra, et al., 2023) (Budianto, 2022) (Budianto, 2022) (Budianto & Dewi, 2022) (Emiliani et al., 2023).

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications regarding Net Profit Margin (NPM) in Islamic and Conventional Banking

There are 885 national journals accredited by Sinta based on the results of data collection using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop originating from the Garuda website (Garba Reference Digital) and Perish/Harzing software during the period 2006 to 2023. The results are as follows:

Table 1. Journal publication data about NPM by year

Year	Amount Publication	Year	Amount Publication	Year	Amount Publication
2006	2	2014	34	2019	86
2007	2	2015	44	2020	129
2009	1	2016	43	2021	158
2011	2	2017	62	2022	179
2012	12	2018	96	2023	19
2013	16				

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Mapping VOSviewer bibliometrics regarding Net Profit Margin (NPM) in Islamic and Conventional Banking

- roi, sample, share, significant for stock prices, spss, data analysis techniques, sampling techniques, autocorrelation test, f test, t test.
- Cluster 3, consists of 50 topic items, namely: analysis technique, analytical method, autocorrelation test, classical assumption testing, coefficient, company, criteria, data analysis method/technique, data collection technique, determination, dividend policy, documentation, effect, f test, heteroscedasticity test, hypothesis testing, idx, independent variable, insignificant effect, manufacturing company, multicollinearity test, multiple linear regression, multiple regression analysis, negative effect, normality test, partial test, population, purposive sampling method/technique, quantitative method/research, quick ratio, research sample, sampling method/technique, secondary data, significant effect/negative effect/positive effect, simultaneous test, stock exchange/price/return, t test, technique.
 - Cluster 4, consists of 5 topic items, namely: beverage company, financial ratio, food, positive effect, share price.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Influence of Net Profit Margin (NPM) on Islamic and Conventional Banking

Library Research study in previous research journals, researchers found 49 influences of NPM on Islamic and Conventional Banking, namely:

- (1) Audit Delay. Audit Delay is the time it takes a company to complete the annual audit process. The lower the NPM, the higher the possibility of audit delays because banks have to ensure that their financial transactions are correct. Therefore, low NPM can cause an increase in audit delay.
- (2) Sharia stock beta. Sharia stock beta shows the level of market risk of a stock compared to the market as a whole. A high NPM indicates that the company is more efficient in generating profits, so it can influence the beta of sharia shares by lowering it. However, this impact may vary depending on other factors such as debt levels and market conditions.
- (3) Capital Adequacy Ratio /CAR. CAR is a measure of a bank's ability to meet its financial obligations. High NPM can increase CAR because the profits generated can be used to strengthen bank capital and improve CAR. Conversely, low NPM can reduce CAR because banks may need to use their capital to cover losses or look for new sources of capital to meet CAR requirements.
- (4) Cash dividends. Cash dividends are the distribution of profits to shareholders in the form of cash. A high NPM can increase a bank's ability to pay cash dividends because the bank has more profits available. However, the decision to pay cash dividends is also influenced by other factors such as bank growth, investment and capital requirements.
- (5) Dividend Payout Ratio /DPR. DPR is the ratio between dividends paid by a company and the net profits generated. High NPM can increase DPR because the company has more profits available to distribute to shareholders. However, dividend payment decisions are also influenced by other factors such as company growth and capital requirements.

(6) Dividend Per Share /DPS. DPS is the amount of dividends paid by the company per share owned by shareholders. High NPM can increase DPS because the company has more profits available to share with shareholders. However, dividend payment decisions are also influenced by other factors such as company growth and capital requirements.

(7) Earnings Per Share /EPS. EPS is the profit per share generated by the company. High NPM can increase EPS because the company has more profits available to share with shareholders. High EPS can increase share prices because investors see it as a sign that the company is performing well. However, this impact may vary depending on other factors such as debt levels and market conditions.

(8) Earnings Management. Earnings Management is a practice carried out by a company to influence financial statements in a way that is detrimental or benefit the company. A high NPM can increase the tendency to carry out earnings management because the company has more profits that can be used to improve its financial reports. However, earnings management practices can be detrimental to the company in the long term because they can reduce investor confidence and the company's reputation. Therefore, earnings management practices should be avoided.

(9) Earnings growth/income growth. High NPM can increase a company's earnings growth because the company has more profits available to invest in business growth. High profits can also provide capital to expand your business, develop new products, or expand your market. However, other factors such as competition, regulations, and economic conditions can affect revenue growth.

(10) Effective Tax Rate. Effective Tax Rate is the ratio between the taxes paid by a company and the income generated. A high NPM can reduce the effective tax rate because the company has more profits that can be used to reduce the tax burden. However, factors such as tax regulations and tax exemptions can also influence the effective tax rate.

(11) Financial Distress. Financial Distress is a condition when a company faces financial difficulties and has difficulty paying debts or operational costs. Low NPM can increase the risk of financial distress because the company may have difficulty paying debts or financing operations if profits are low. However, factors such as risk management and portfolio diversification can help reduce the risk of financial distress.

(12) Growth Ratio. Growth Ratio is the ratio between the company's new revenue and old revenue. High NPM can increase the growth ratio because the company has more profits that can be invested in new businesses or expansion. However, factors such as business risk and market conditions can also influence the growth ratio.

(13) Stock price. A high NPM can provide a positive signal to investors and analysts that the company has the ability to generate good profits. This can increase investor interest and encourage share prices to rise. However, other factors such as economic conditions, competition, and monetary policy can also influence stock prices.

(14) Closing stock price. The closing share price is the last share price at the end of the trading session on the stock exchange. A high NPM can increase the

closing price of shares because investors tend to be more interested in companies that generate high profits. However, factors such as economic conditions and market sentiment can also influence the closing price of a stock.

(15) Bond prices. Bond prices depend on factors such as interest rates and credit risk. A high NPM can increase a company's ability to pay debt and obtain a better credit rating, thereby reducing credit risk and increasing bond prices. However, factors such as bond market conditions and market risk can also influence bond prices.

(16) Income smoothing/profit smoothing. Income smoothing is the practice of companies to adjust earnings over different periods to create the impression that the company's earnings are more stable than they actually are. A high NPM can make it easier for a company to carry out income smoothing because the company has more profits available to transfer to different periods. However, this practice can pose risks because it can mask real financial problems and damage investor confidence. Therefore, income smoothing practices must be carried out carefully and transparently.

(17) Dividend policy. High NPM can increase a company's ability to pay dividends. This is because the company has more profits available to share with shareholders. Therefore, a company can adopt a more aggressive dividend policy if its NPM is high. However, dividend policy is also influenced by other factors such as market conditions and company strategy.

(18) Debt policy. A high NPM can strengthen a company's financial position and increase the company's ability to obtain debt at lower interest rates. This is because the company has the ability to repay debt and pay interest easily from the profits generated. However, companies must also pay attention to debt-related risks, such as credit risk and interest rate risk.

(19) Financial performance. High NPM can indicate good financial performance for the company. This is because NPM measures a company's ability to generate profits from the revenue generated. On the other hand, low NPM can indicate problems in the company's business and trigger corrective action from company management.

(20) Timeliness of submission of financial reports. A high NPM can make it easier for companies to prepare and submit financial reports in a timely manner. This is because companies have the ability to employ adequate experts and technological tools to prepare and audit financial reports. However, the timeliness of submitting financial reports is also influenced by other factors such as regulatory policies and the complexity of the company's business.

(21) Zakat ability. A high NPM can increase a company's ability to pay zakat. This is because the company has more profits available to pay out as zakat. Therefore, the company can strengthen its position as a financial institution that is oriented towards sharia values and principles.

(22) Operating profit. High NPM can increase a company's operating profits. This is because NPM measures a company's ability to generate profits from the revenue generated. On the other hand, low NPM can indicate problems in the company's business and trigger corrective action from company management.

(23) Competitive profit. High NPM can also increase a company's competitive profits. This is because companies can offer more competitive products and services at lower prices or provide greater profits to shareholders. However, competitive profits are also influenced by other factors such as market conditions and company strategy.

(24) Liquidity. High NPM can strengthen a company's financial position and increase liquidity. This is because the company has the ability to pay debt and obtain cheaper funding. However, companies must also pay attention to risks related to liquidity such as market liquidity risk and financing liquidity risk.

(25) Profit management. High NPM can provide incentives for company management to carry out earnings management. This is because high NPM can improve company performance and obtain bonuses or other incentives from shareholders or management. However, excessive earnings management can result in long-term losses for the company.

(26) Working capital. High NPM can increase the company's working capital. This is because the company has more profits available to spend as investments in current assets such as inventory or receivables. With sufficient working capital, the company can strengthen its position in meeting operational needs and generating greater income.

(27) Paid-up capital. A high NPM can increase the company's paid-in capital. This is because the company has the ability to generate sufficient profits to be distributed to shareholders or saved as paid-in capital. With sufficient paid-in capital, a company can strengthen its position in obtaining funds from other parties and reduce the risk of bankruptcy.

(28) The value of the company. High NPM can increase company value. This is because a high NPM can indicate that the company has the ability to generate large and stable profits from the income generated. In the long term, company value can be influenced by other factors such as economic growth, market competition, and risk factors.

(29) Net Profit Margin/NPM. A high NPM shows that the company has a larger profit margin. In a banking context, this can indicate that the company has the ability to generate net profits that are greater than revenue. In other words, the higher the NPM, the greater the possibility that the company will generate high net profits.

(30) Increased profitability. High NPM can help a company improve its financial capabilities. The greater the NPM, the more money available to reinvest into the company, increasing the company's ability to generate greater net profits in the future. This can also increase the company's ability to pay dividends to shareholders.

(31) Online and non-online sales. High NPM can give confidence to customers and investors. This can help increase online and non-online sales, because customers and investors tend to have more confidence in companies that generate high and efficient net profits.

(32) Change in profit. Changes in banking profits can be influenced by various factors, including NPM. A high NPM can help a company generate greater net

profits, while a low NPM can reduce net profits. Therefore, high NPM can help increase a company's net profit.

(33) Profit growth. A high NPM can show that banks are able to generate large net profits from their revenues. Thus, banks with high NPM can show good financial performance and can achieve good profit growth. This can provide a positive signal for investors and can increase their trust in banking, thereby strengthening company value and generating the potential for greater profit growth in the future.

(34) Revenue growth. A high NPM can show a bank's ability to generate net profits from revenue. Thus, banking income growth can be influenced by high NPM, because banks with high NPM tend to be able to invest more money to increase their income. This can be seen in the form of adding products and services, developing new markets, or expanding the customer base.

(35) Growth of own capital. High NPM can help banks increase their own capital. The greater the NPM, the more money available to invest back into the company, increasing capabilities companies to increase their own capital. In the long term, this can help banks improve their ability to distribute credit and expand their customer base.

(36) Banking credit distribution. A high NPM can help banks improve their ability to distribute credit to customers who meet the requirements. Banks with high NPM tend to have more resources to use in extending credit to their customers. This can expand the customer base and increase banking revenues in the long term.

(37) Risk disclosure. A high NPM can show that banks have good efficiency in generating net profits from their revenues. However, a high NPM can also indicate that banks are more susceptible to risk. Therefore, banks that have high NPM must continue to carry out appropriate risk disclosures to provide transparency regarding the risks they face.

(38) Disclosure of social responsibility. Banks that have a high NPM can show that they have the ability to pay attention to corporate social responsibility. As part of corporate social responsibility, banks can use their profits to provide support and contributions to society and the surrounding environment, such as charity programs or other social activities. Thus, high NPM can strengthen the company's positive image in the eyes of the public.

(39) Dividend payments. Banks with high NPM can have the ability to pay higher dividends to their shareholders. This can increase shareholder confidence in the company and increase investor interest in investing in the company. In addition, higher dividend payments can also increase company value and produce greater potential profit growth in the future.

(40) Price Earning Ratio /PER. High NPM can affect the PER value of banking. PER is the ratio between share price and net profit per share, and is an important indicator in assessing share valuation. Banks with high NPM can have a higher PER because of their greater net profit per share. This can make banking shares more attractive to investors because they can provide the potential for greater returns.

(41) Price to Book Value/PBV. PBV is the ratio between share price and book value per share, which is used to measure company valuation. High NPM can affect PBV because greater net income can increase book value per share, which can increase PBV. Therefore, banks with high NPM tend to have higher PBV, which can make their shares more attractive to investors.

(42) Return On Assets/ROA. ROA is a financial ratio that measures the efficiency of using company assets in generating profits. High NPM can increase ROA because greater net profit can increase the company's return on assets. Thus, banks with high NPM tend to have higher ROA, which indicates better financial performance.

(43) Return On Equity /ROE. ROE is a financial ratio that measures the efficiency of using a company's equity in generating profits. High NPM can increase ROE because greater net profit can increase the company's return on equity. Thus, banking with NPM high ones tend to have higher ROE, which indicates better financial performance.

(44) Return On Investment/ROI. ROI is a financial ratio that measures the return on investment generated by a company. High NPM can increase ROI because greater net profit can increase the company's return on investment. Thus, banks with high NPM tend to have higher ROI, which indicates better financial performance.

(45) returns. Stock returns refer to the profits generated by investors in the form of dividends and increases in share value. High NPM can increase stock returns because larger net profits can increase dividend payments and increase share prices. Thus, banks with high NPM tend to have higher stock returns.

(46) Economic profitability. Economic profitability refers to a company's ability to efficiently generate profits from invested capital. High NPM can increase economic profitability because larger net profits can increase returns on invested capital. Thus, banks with high NPM tend to have higher economic profitability.

(47) Capital structure. Capital structure refers to the proportion between share capital and debt used to finance company operations. A high NPM can affect the capital structure because larger net profits can be used to pay debt and/or finance company expansion without having to issue additional share capital. Thus, banks with high NPM tend to have a better capital structure.

(48) Underpricing. Underpricing refers to an IPO stock price that is lower than fair value. High NPM can influence underpricing because greater net income can indicate good financial performance and increase investor interest in company shares. Thus, banks with high NPM tend to have lower underpricing.

(49) Debt. High NPM can influence debt taking by banks because larger net profits can be used to pay debt or obtain additional debt to finance company expansion. However, banks also need to pay attention to the debt to equity ratio and credit risk when making debt decisions. Therefore, the effect of NPM on debt can vary depending on the company's financial condition and strategy.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Determinant Variables of Net Profit Margin/NPM in Islamic and Conventional Banking

Library Research study in previous research journals, researchers found 41 determinant variables of NPM in Islamic and Conventional Banking, namely:

(1) Fixed assets. Fixed assets are part of a bank's balance sheet which includes assets owned by the bank for a period of more than one year, such as buildings, machinery and vehicles. An increase in fixed assets can have a positive impact on NPM, because it can increase operational efficiency and banking productivity.

(2) Acquisition. Acquisition is one of the banking strategies to acquire other banks, with the aim of expanding the business and increasing profits. If the acquisition is carried out correctly, it can increase banking NPM. However, if the acquisition is carried out hastily or inappropriately, it could have a negative impact on NPM.

(3) Operational Costs to Operational Income/BOPO. Operational costs (BOPO) are costs incurred by banks to run daily business, such as employee salaries, building rental costs and electricity costs. If BOPO increases, this could have a negative impact on NPM, because it will reduce the net profit generated by banks.

(4) Promotion costs. Promotional costs are costs incurred by banks to promote products or services offered to customers. If promotional costs increase, this can have a positive or negative impact on NPM, depending on the effectiveness of the promotional strategy implemented.

(5) Cash Ratio. The cash ratio measures a company's ability to pay short-term debt using cash or cash equivalents. A high cash ratio shows the company's ability to manage cash well and reduce the risk of bankruptcy. This can have a positive impact on NPM because companies have a tendency to focus more on increasing net profit rather than solving liquidity problems.

(6) Current Ratio. The current ratio measures the company's ability to pay short-term debt using current assets. A high current ratio shows the company's ability to overcome short-term obligations and increase investor confidence. This can have a positive impact on NPM because companies can focus more on business activities that generate profits rather than facing the risk of bankruptcy.

(7) Cost Efficiency Ratio. The cost efficiency ratio measures the efficiency of a company's costs in generating revenue. A low cost efficiency ratio shows the company's ability to manage operational costs effectively and increase profitability. This can have a positive impact on NPM because lower operational costs can increase net profit.

(8) Covid-19. The Covid-19 pandemic could have a negative impact on banking NPM due to a decline in economic activity and an increase in credit risk. Banks are also facing pressure to provide credit payment relief to customers affected by the pandemic. However, banks can take strategic steps to overcome the impact of the pandemic, such as reducing operational costs, increasing product and service diversification, and increasing digitalization. This can help banks to maintain or even increase NPM in the long term.

(9) Third Party Funds/DPK. DPK measures the company's funding sources from customers or other third parties. The larger the TPF, the greater the funding sources available to banks, which can increase the company's ability to provide credit and increase interest income. This can have a positive impact on NPM because it increases the potential interest income earned.

(10) Debt to Total Asset Ratio /DAR. DAR measures the ratio of a company's debt to its total assets. A low DAR indicates that the company has lower financial risk and greater ability to manage risk. This can have a positive impact on NPM because it reduces interest costs and the risk of bankruptcy.

(11) Debt to Equity Ratio /DER. DER measures the ratio of company debt to company equity. A high DER indicates that the company relies on high debt funding and has greater financial risk. This can have a negative impact on NPM due to higher interest rates and increased risk of bankruptcy.

(12) Production cost efficiency. Production cost efficiency measures a company's ability to generate revenue with effective production costs. The more efficient production costs, the greater the company's potential net profit. This can have a positive impact on NPM because it increases the net profit generated by the company.

(13) Environmental Performance. Environmental Performance measures the extent to which a company pays attention to environmental impacts in its business activities. Companies that pay attention to environmental factors can show a commitment to being a responsible company and can improve the company's reputation in the eyes of consumers. This can have a positive impact on NPM because it can increase consumer confidence and increase business income.

(14) Fee Based Income. Fee Based Income refers to the income a company obtains from fee-based services such as insurance services, investment services and financial consulting services. Income derived from fee-based income is stable and low risk, so it can help increase NPM consistently.

(15) Good Corporate Governance /GCG. Good Corporate Governance refers to company management practices that are transparent, fair and responsible. Companies with good GCG can increase public and investor trust and reduce financial and reputation risks. This can have a positive impact on NPM because it can attract investors and increase business income.

(16) Inflation. Inflation is a general increase in the prices of goods and services. Inflation can affect a company's financial performance because it can increase the company's operational costs such as interest costs, operational costs and other expenses. Therefore, high inflation can have a negative impact on NPM because it increases the company's operational costs.

(17) Problematic credit. Non-performing loans can have a negative impact on banking NPM. This is because when a bank gives credit to a debtor who is then unable to pay it back, the bank must experience a loss and reduce the NPM. Problematic loans can also force banks to increase reserves for impairment losses on uncollectible loans (PCL). This can affect banking net profits which in turn can affect NPM.

(18) Institutional ownership. Institutional ownership can influence banking NPM because institutional ownership can influence banking management and the strategies taken. Strong and stable institutional ownership can increase investor confidence and banking credibility, which in turn can increase income and NPM.

(19) Liquidity. Liquidity refers to a company's ability to meet its short-term financial obligations. Sufficient liquidity can help banks obtain lower borrowing costs and minimize the risk of default on loans. This can have a positive impact on NPM because it can increase income and reduce borrowing costs.

(20) Gap Management. Gap Management refers to the management of interest rate risks faced by banks. Interest rate risk can affect a bank's interest margin, which in turn can affect NPM. Banks need to manage interest rate risk appropriately through effective Gap management. This can help banks earn better profits and increase NPM.

(21) Foreign Exchange Management in Assets and Liability Management /ALMA. ALMA is a risk management process related to managing a portfolio of banking assets and liabilities, including managing foreign exchange risk. Good foreign exchange management can help banks better manage foreign exchange risks effectively, minimize the risk of loss, and optimize profits. This can have a positive impact on NPM by increasing revenue and reducing costs.

(22) Exchange rate/exchange rate. The exchange rate can affect banking NPM because it can affect interest margins and profits on foreign exchange transactions. An increase in the exchange rate can increase interest margins because it can allow banks to obtain higher interest rates on loans provided. However, if exchange rates continue to fluctuate, banks must also pay attention to exchange rate risks and manage them appropriately.

(23) Non Performing Loans /NPL. NPL refers to loans that are not repaid by debtors or loans that do not pay on time. NPL can affect banking NPM because it can cause losses and reduce interest income. Banks must carry out good credit management to reduce NPL risk and minimize the impact on NPM.

(24) Operating Expenses and Sales. Operating expenses and sales can affect banking NPM. Low operational costs can help banks increase NPM by earning higher income or by minimizing costs. High sales can help banks earn higher income and increase NPM. Therefore, banks must focus on controlling operational costs and increasing sales to increase NPM.

(25) Operational Efficiency Ratio /OER. OER is a ratio that measures the level of efficiency of a bank's operational costs. The lower the OER, the more efficient the bank's operational costs. OER can influence NPM because the lower the operational costs, the greater the profits the bank can obtain, so it can increase NPM.

(26) Receivables collection period. The receivables collection period is the time required by a bank to collect receivables from customers. The shorter the receivables collection period, the faster the bank can flow cash into the bank's treasury, so that the bank can increase liquidity and gain profits more quickly, thereby increasing NPM.

(27) Cash turnover. Cash turnover is a ratio that measures how quickly a bank flows its cash. The higher the cash turnover, the faster the bank will channel its cash and the faster the bank will make a profit, so it can increase NPM.

(28) Working capital turnover. WCT is a ratio that measures the efficiency of a bank's use of working capital in generating income. The higher the working capital turnover, the more efficient the bank is in using its working capital, so that it can increase income and NPM.

(29) Cash receivables turnover. Cash receivables turnover is a ratio that measures how quickly a company can collect its receivables from customers. The faster a company collects its receivables, the more liquid cash the company has. This can affect NPM in banking, because the more liquid cash it has, the greater the company's ability to obtain income from its operational activities, so that it can increase NPM.

(30) Zakat. Zakat is a religious obligation for companies operating in the financial sector. Zakat is removed from company profits and paid to parties entitled to receive it. Zakat payments can affect NPM in banking directly and indirectly. Directly, zakat payments can reduce company profits, thereby reducing NPM. However, indirectly, zakat payments can also increase public trust in the company, which can influence the company's future revenue and NPM.

(31) Total asset turnover. Total asset turnover is a ratio that measures how effectively a company uses its assets to generate sales. The higher the total asset turnover, the more effective the company is in using its assets. This can affect NPM in banking, because the more effective a company is in using its assets, the greater the company's ability to obtain income from its operational activities, so that it can increase NPM.

(32) Use of standard costs. Using standard costs can help companies control production costs and increase operational efficiency. This can affect NPM in banking, because the more effective a company is in controlling its production costs, the greater the company's ability to obtain income from its operational activities, so that it can increase NPM.

(33) Sales growth. Sales growth is one of the factors that can influence NPM in banking. If sales growth increases, the company can obtain greater income from its operational activities, thereby increasing NPM. However, sales growth that is too fast can also affect NPM by increasing operational costs, so companies must manage their operational costs well so as not to reduce NPM.

(34) Quick Ratio. The quick ratio is a ratio that measures a company's ability to meet its short-term obligations with the most liquid current assets. A high quick ratio indicates that the company has high liquidity and can meet its short-term obligations quickly. This can affect NPM in banking, because the more liquid the company, the greater the company's ability to obtain income from its operational activities, so that it can increase NPM.

(35) Return On Assets/ROA. ROA is a ratio that measures a company's efficiency in generating profits from the use of its assets. The higher the ROA, the more efficient the company is in managing its assets to generate profits. This can affect NPM in banking, because the more efficient a company is in

using its assets, the greater the company's ability to obtain income from its operational activities, so that it can increase NPM.

(36) Return On Equity /ROE. ROE is a ratio that measures a company's efficiency in generating profits from capital invested by shareholders. The higher the ROE, the more efficient the company is in using the capital invested by its shareholders to generate profits. This can affect NPM in banking, because the more efficient a company is in using capital invested by its shareholders, the greater the company's ability to obtain income from its operational activities, so that it can increase NPM.

(37) Receivable Turn Over. Receivable Turn Over is a ratio that measures a company's effectiveness in collecting receivables from its customers. The higher this ratio, the more effective the company is in collecting receivables, thereby increasing the company's liquidity and income. This can affect NPM in banking, because the higher the company's liquidity, the greater the company's ability to obtain income from its operational activities, so that it can increase NPM.

(38) Service Quality Gap in providing credit. Service Quality Gap is the difference between customer expectations of the quality of service provided by the company and customer perceptions of the quality of service actually provided by the company. If the Service Quality Gap in providing credit is low. This means that customers' perceptions of the company's service quality are in line with their expectations, which will increase customer trust in the company. This can affect NPM in banking, because the higher customer trust, the greater the possibility of customers to use the company's products and services, so that it can increase NPM.

(39) Interest rate. Interest rates can affect NPM in banking directly and indirectly. Directly, high interest rates can increase a company's interest income, thereby increasing NPM. However, indirectly, high interest rates can also affect credit demand from customers, so that it can affect the company's revenue and NPM. Interest rates can also affect a company's capital costs and operational costs, which can affect NPM.

(40) Company size. Company size can influence NPM in banking. Larger companies tend to have greater economies of scale and the ability to optimize their operational costs. This can increase the company's efficiency in generating profits, thereby increasing NPM. However, larger companies also tend to have greater operational risk, so companies must manage risk well so as not to reduce NPM.

(41) Sales volume. Sales volume can affect NPM in banking directly and indirectly. Directly, the greater the sales volume, the greater the company's income, so it can increase NPM. However, indirectly, companies must also consider the costs associated with increasing sales volume, such as marketing costs and production costs, which can affect the company's profit margin and NPM.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows: first, based on mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding the Net Profit Margin (NPM) ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking during the period of From 2006 to 2022, originating from the accredited national

journal Sinta, there were 885 published journal articles. Second, based on VOSviewer bibliometric study mapping, the network visualization results regarding the NPM ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking are divided into 4 clusters and 175 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 65 topics, cluster 2 consists of 55 topics, cluster 3 consists of 50 topics, and cluster 4 consists of 5 topics. Third, based on mapping Library Research studies, there are 49 topics related to the influence of the NPM ratio on Islamic and Conventional Banking, namely: audit delay, beta of sharia shares, Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR, cash dividends, Dividend Payout Ratio/DPR, Dividend Per Share /DPS, Earning Per Share /EPS, earnings management, income growth, effective tax rate, financial distress, growth ratio, stock prices, closing stock prices, bond prices, income smoothing, dividend policy, debt policy, financial performance, timeliness of financial report submission, zakat capability, operating profit, competitive profit, liquidity, earnings management, working capital, paid-in capital, company value, Net Profit Margin/NPM, increased profitability, online and non-online sales, changes in profits, profit growth, income growth, own capital growth, bank credit distribution, risk disclosure, social responsibility disclosure, dividend payments, Price Earning Ratio /PER, Price to Book Value /PBV, Return On Assets /ROA, Return On Equity /ROE, Return On Investment/ROI, stock returns, economic profitability, capital structure, underpricing, and debt.

And there are 41 topics related to the determinants of the EPS ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking, namely: fixed assets, acquisitions, Operational Costs to Operating Income/BOPO, promotional costs, cash ratio, current ratio, Cost Efficiency Ratio, Covid-19, Party Funds Third/DPK, Debt to Total Asset Ratio /DAR, Debt to Equity Ratio /DER, production cost efficiency, environmental performance, Fee Based Income, Good Corporate Governance /GCG, inflation, non-performing loans, institutional ownership, liquidity, gap management, foreign exchange management in Assets and Liability Management/ALMA, exchange rates, Non Performing Loans/NPL, Operating Expenses and Sales, Operational Efficiency Ratio/OER, receivables collection period, turnover cash, Working Capital Turnover/WCT, cash receivables turnover, total asset turnover, use of standard costs, sales growth, quick ratio, Return On Assets/ROA, Return On Equity/ROE, Receivable Turn Over, Service Quality Gap in delivery credit, interest rates, company size, sales volume, and zakat.

Limitations

The scope of the research only covers the Net Profit Margin (NPM) ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking during the period 2006 to 2022. The publications studied only come from accredited national journals Sinta 1-6. These limitations mean that this research does not yet describe the NPM ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking as a whole. Apart from that, there are several international journals indexed by Scopus that have not been included in this research, whereas these journals are needed to compare the NPM ratio in Indonesia and other countries.

Suggestion

It is recommended that further research use a larger data sample, both from national accredited journals Sinta and international journals indexed by Scopus, so that it can explain a broader research mapping, considering the

limitations of the data sample in this study and can add a longer time span for research data so that it can The following research results were obtained: first, it is hoped that the mapping results will show a higher and broader level of generalization. Second, the results of the Library Research study can be explained in a more complex way.

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